

Marco Vanucci

AUTOMATA

The progressive encapsulation of human knowledge into technical systems has accelerated automation, expanding “the number of operations which we can perform without thinking.”¹ Ranging from mechanical tools to AI-driven algorithms, this process has increased efficiency, scalability, and complexity in decision-making, while steadily altering the role of human agency. As technical systems evolve toward self-learning and autonomous determination, a central question arises: to what extent is human agency being displaced?

Autonomy implies self-governance: the capacity to establish one’s own principles and act according to them. Automation, by contrast, is the execution of predefined operations according to externally imposed conditions. While it optimises tasks, it remains fundamentally dependent on human intent. Or at least, it has until now.

With the rise of machine learning and predictive algorithms, technical systems are shifting toward self-regulation. Agency does not disappear in this process; it migrates: from production toward curation, from control toward evaluation, from authorship toward the construction of frameworks. The central question this raises is not whether automation is becoming more sophisticated, but whether it signals a categorical shift toward a new kind of autonomy altogether.

Bruno Zevi’s sceptical response to Luigi Moretti’s parametric experiments in 1960, “Electronic brains? No, calculating machines,”² already posed the question that now returns with renewed urgency. Contemporary

¹ A. N. Whitehead, *An Introduction to Mathematics*, Williams and Norgate, London, 1911, p. 61.

² B. Zevi, “Cervelli elettronici? No macchine calcolatrici,” *L’architettura: cronaca e storia*, 6, 62, 1960, pp. 508–509.

systems, however, are no longer calculating machines in Zevi's sense. Where Polanyi observed that "we can know more than we can tell,"³ the opacity of machine learning inverts this condition: we can tell, or rather our machines can output, far more than we understand. The shift is structural: from deterministic automata, in which outcomes remain traceable to explicit rules, to probabilistic generative systems, in which behaviour emerges from statistical inference across spaces of a complexity that exceeds human intuition.

Yet the apparent novelty of these developments obscures a longer history of artificial cognition embedded within technical media. As Andrew Witt argues in this issue, artificial memory constitutes a fundamental precondition for automata, functioning simultaneously as a technical medium and as a spatial device. In the seventeenth century, architects played a pivotal and largely overlooked role in this history: the French architect and hydraulic engineer Salomon de Caus developed reprogrammable musical automata whose memory architectures operated at building scale, making architectural thinking an essential condition for computational invention. These systems did not merely execute predefined sequences; they stored, organised, and reactivated information, anticipating contemporary concerns with encoding, retrieval, and machine readability. The architect thus emerges not only as a designer of form, but as a transdisciplinary inventor at the origin of machine memory itself.

Antoine Picon argues that artificial intelligence must be understood not merely as a new set of tools, but as a condition that transforms the conceptual foundations of architectural practice. Rather than asking what AI can do for design in instrumental terms, he examines how it compels a reconsideration of agency, authorship, intention, and responsibility. Central to his argument is the tension between the growing dominance of efficiency in contemporary design and the irreducible dimension of architectural intention that Boullée once called the "poetry of art," a quality that no process of technical optimisation can fully account for.

The decisive shift, Alisa Andrasek contends, is not from human to machine agency, but from architecture as representation to architecture as cognition. Intelligence becomes distributed across human, computational, and material systems, while creativity is reframed as the navigation of high-dimensional possibility spaces. What remains irreducible in this

³ M. Polanyi, *The Tacit Dimension*, Doubleday & Company, Garden City, New York, 1966.

expanded field is aesthetic cognition: the trained capacity to recognise latent order within configurations that have no prior typological grounding, to commit to a trajectory before its consequences are fully known. This framework positions the architect not as author or operator, but as the irreplaceable cognitive filter within a generative field that no machine can navigate alone. This understanding of distributed intelligence finds a collective and pedagogical dimension in the interview with Theodore Spyropoulos, whose work frames architecture as an ecology of interacting systems in which agency emerges through distributed, time-based processes rather than individual intention. The architect's role shifts from authoring form to staging conditions for interaction and adaptive formation. The question of whether contemporary AI systems merely recombine precedents or genuinely exceed them runs through several contributions to this issue. Surrealist automatism, Simon Weir argues, offers architecture not a historical technique but a cognitive framework: one that externalises perception, association, and thought beyond conscious control, and that extends naturally to AI-assisted design insofar as such systems reorganise design thinking in ways that exceed simple instrumentality. From a different angle, Matias del Campo proposes inferentialism as a methodology grounded in Simondon's critique of hylomorphism, where form does not precede its realisation but crystallises through probabilistic transductive processes distributed across human cognition, computational systems, and material environments. The most direct challenge to established positions comes from Philippe Morel, who draws on information theory, the history of computability, and recent results in high-dimensional geometry to argue that generative AI cannot adequately be described as a machine of imitation. Under a strict geometric definition, such systems are constrained to extrapolate beyond the convex hull of their training data, driven to invent as a mathematical necessity rather than an intentional act. As Mario Carpo notes, the mechanisms of imitation have become largely unintelligible within contemporary discourse,⁴ and his interview in this issue offers a counterpoint to Morel's argument, framing one of the central debates the issue sets out to explore.

The question of authorship finds its most direct and provocative formulation in Graham Harman's contribution, which challenges the

⁴ M. Carpo, "The Imitation Machine," in C. Ratti (ed.), *Catalogue of Biennale Architettura 2025. Intelligens. Natural. Artificial. Collective*, Edizioni La Biennale di Venezia, Venice, 2025, 1, pp. 190–193.

romantic image of the writer or designer generating work from nothing as a solitary creative act. This image, he argues, mistakes a transient historical condition for an essential one. What is genuinely essential to intellectual and creative life is not the capacity to produce *ex nihilo* but the capacity to discriminate, evaluate, and refine: connoisseurship rather than creation. The human role is not abolished but relocated, from the generation of drafts to the exercise of judgement over an abundance of generated possibilities, a shift that demands more cultivated taste, not less.

Klaus Wiegler approaches the question of autonomous technology from a philosophical perspective, arguing that technical systems access reality only in a typological manner, registering statistical regularities while remaining unable to grasp what is singular, eventful, and irreducibly situated. The attempt to eliminate resistance through autonomous systems does not produce freedom but a corresponding loss of reality, and with it a loss of agency itself.

The political dimension of this loss is taken up directly in the interview with Bernard Cache, whose insistence on open-source infrastructures, shared syntactic frameworks, and public digital standards reframes automation as a question of sovereignty rather than efficiency. The increasing dependence on proprietary platforms, he argues, risks dispossessing architects of their own work. Who controls the digital environments of practice is not a technical question but a fundamentally political one.

The contributions gathered in this issue of *Khōrein* share a common wager: that the automaton need not be understood as a servant of efficiency or a threat to authorship, but as an unruly, generative condition that demands new forms of judgement, responsibility, and collective deliberation. What is at stake is not only how architecture is produced, but who gets to participate in the construction of its meaning.